

Flower Image Detection using Machine Learning

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Abstract - We frequently become fascinated about flowers when we see them. However, the typical person won't be able to identify them if they have little to no experience with flower arrangements. The proper flower acquisition model enabled by convolutional neural networks is investigated in this paper (CNN). The jpeg-formatted photographs we utilised to build the database were taken from Google. The downloaded files are then added to the drive that contains the merging file. Three train, test, and work folders are used to store and organise images. There have been numerous extraction methods suggested up to this point, which might be more beneficial for other floral types than for a trained database.

Keywords—flower detection, Convolutional Neural Network, MaxPooling2D.

I. INTRODUCTION

Flowers are among God's most beautiful creations, and there are a wide variety of them. Numerous flowers are being identified for the first time based on their colour, texture, and shape..

The planned detection will be carried out with the use of machine learning, with a primary emphasis on the more in-depth aspects of deep learning. A dataset that will be utilised in the project will be created by us. In this era of technological advancement, many previously impossible things have become possible by applying practical understanding to global issues. We also know that flowers are used in many different industries, including the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. The majority of flowers, according to ancient ayurveda, have healing powers. In this article, convolutional neural networks are introduced to more precisely identify the flower in the image.

Images saved in jpg, jpeg, and png formats can be used to create databases. First, pick three different kinds of flowers: rose, hibiscus, and lotus. Following the creation of the database, discovery must be conducted. And CNN's detecting capabilities. Three folders with images should be created from the database. Category has to be mentioned. Three sections—train set, test set, and valid set—make up the database. Additionally, the data sets are broken up based on the names of the flowers. We must file a file and do the experimental training at the proper rate after importing the libraries.

The method for detecting flowers that uses:

- Flower Recognition: flowers can be detect using its shape, texture and color.
- Image Preprocessing: steps taken to format the images before they are used in modeling training and description.
- Train-Test Split: the dataset contains images splitted with a ratio of 70- 20%.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Pavan Kumar Mishral uses digital page photos and flowers to identify crops silently and automatically. They offered suggestions for categorising them into different groups that may be distinguished by factors like colour, volume, and cell element. There are three further sections within each section. Based on the RGB component's retrieved features, the comparison process begins. The second step makes use of rotation properties, sphericity, area convexity, and perimeter convexity. The final category is based on.

2. Grayscale photos are created by converting RGB photographs to grayscale images. To enhance images, a variety of approaches are used, including histogram alignment and contrast adjusting.

3. Asma Najjar, Ezzeddine Zagrouba, and Amira Ben Mabrouk, Using a multi-kernel framework and SVM classifier, they provided a novel method of extracting colour elements based on SURF points of interest and integrated elements in this study.

III. MOTIVATION

This research and task work have a unique motivation at its core. Everyone has never heard of the name or species of a flower when we have seen a variety of unknown flowers in various locations. Then I consider utilising machine learning to recognise flowers. For this, several research strategies are used..

IV. METHODOLOGY

Finding a machine learning model to recognise the flower using the dataset is the aim of this paper. The image will be displayed and the model should be able to recognise the name of the flower. Two training and testing data sets are created from the dataset. For the model to learn accurately, more data should be used during training. The building is:

Figure 1: Flower Detection Methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Image Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Detection of image
6. Result

A. Data Collection: The user has a dataset for floral image detection. Just a few flowers were utilised for the detection. Rose, hibiscus, and lotus are the three types of flowers utilised for this. The model is trained using the attributes of this dataset.

B. Image Pre-processing: The first step in every machine learning technique is this one. Before the photos could be

utilised as the training dataset, they had to be pre-processed.

Machine Learning:

The machine learning is used to detect flower using Deep learning and CNN architecture.

CNN Architecture:

Convolutional neural network is used for the flower detection. The main purpose of CNNs is to perform challenging image-driven pattern recognition tasks, particularly because to their exact yet straightforward design.

1. Flower Detection: Flower detection can be done mainly identifying color, texture and shape of the flower.

2. Convolutional layer: In order to extract different elements from input photos, this layer is the first one to be employed. This layer performs the mathematical operation of convolution between an input image and a certain $M \times M$ size filter. The dot output is obtained by swiping the filter over the input image and taking it between the filter and portions of the input picture that are proportional to the filter size ($M \times M$)

3. Pooling Layer: A pooling layer comes after the convolutional layer. This layer's main goal is to lower the convolved feature map's size in order to save on computational expenses. This is done independently on each feature map and by reducing the links between layers. There are various sorts of pooling procedures depending on the mechanism employed.

4. MaxPooling 2D: The function of publicly combining the biggest, or largest, value in each piece of map for each element, is known as mass compilation or multiplication. The outcomes are feature maps with low or compact sample sizes that emphasise the episode's most prevalent feature, rather than the feature's appearance in the middle of the map in the case of a medium combination.

V. BUILD MODEL

The primary phase in flower picture detection is model construction. The algorithms are used by the user when developing the model. The actions required are:

1. Import the Libraries that are necessary.

```
import os, sys
from google.colab import drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')
os.chdir('/content/drive/My Drive/Colab Notebooks/')
sys.path.append('/content/drive/My Drive/Colab Notebooks/')
Mounted at /content/drive

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import os
import cv2
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dense, Dropout, Activation, Flatten
from keras.layers import Convolution2D, MaxPooling2D
from keras.utils import np_utils
```

2. Visualization of images category based on the number of images in each category flowers via a barplot

```
import seaborn as sns
category_names = os.listdir(path)
nb_categories = len(categories)
train_images = []

for category in categories:
    folder = path + "/" + category
    train_images.append(len(os.listdir(folder)))

sns.barplot(y=category_names, x=train_images).set_title("Number Of Images Per Ca
```

3. Printing images based on category.

```
for category in categories:
    fig, _ = plt.subplots(3,4)
    fig.suptitle(category)
    fig.patch.set_facecolor('xkcd:white')
    for k, v in enumerate(os.listdir(path+'/'+category))[:12]:
        img = plt.imread(path+'/'+category+'/' +v)
        plt.subplot(3, 4, k+1)
        plt.axis('off')
        plt.imshow(img)
    plt.show()
```

4. Displaying the minimum and maximum height and width size of each categories.

```
shape0 = []
shape1 = []

for category in categories:
    for files in os.listdir(path+'/'+category):
        shape0.append(plt.imread(path+'/'+category+'/' + files).shape[0])
        shape1.append(plt.imread(path+'/'+category+'/' + files).shape[1])
    print(category, ' => height min : ', min(shape0), 'width min : ', min(shape1))
    print(category, ' => height max : ', max(shape0), 'width max : ', max(shape1))
    shape0 = []
    shape1 = []
```

5. Calling images in to the file via their path address and not in to the colored format.

```
data = []
labels = []
imagePaths = []
HEIGHT = 145
WIDTH = 182
N_CHANNELS = 3
for k, category in enumerate(categories):
    for f in os.listdir(path+'/'+category):
        imagePaths.append([path+'/'+category+'/' +f, k])

import random
random.shuffle(imagePaths)
print(imagePaths[:10])
for imagePath in imagePaths:
    image = cv2.imread(imagePath[0])
    image = cv2.resize(image, (WIDTH, HEIGHT))
    data.append(image)
    label = imagePath[1]
    labels.append(label)

[['/content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/FLOWERS/train/lotus/12.jpg', 0], [
```

6. Displaying images of each category in RGB format

```
fig, _ = plt.subplots(3,4)
fig.suptitle("Sample Input")
fig.patch.set_facecolor('xkcd:white')
for i in range(12):
    plt.subplot(3,4, i+1)
    plt.imshow(data[i])
    plt.axis('off')
    plt.title(categories[labels[i]])
plt.show()
```

7. Printing shape of tests set and train set.

```
trainY = np_utils.to_categorical(trainY, 8)
print(trainX.shape)
print(testX.shape)
print(trainY.shape)
print(testY.shape)
```

8. Displaying the features of the model built

```
model = Sequential()

model.add(Convolution2D(32, (2, 2), activation='relu', input_shape=(HEIGHT, WIDTH, N_CHANNELS)))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
model.add(Convolution2D(32, (2, 2), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.25))
model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(128, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(8, activation='softmax'))
model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy', optimizer='adam', metrics=['accuracy'])
print(model.summary())
```

9. Plotting model.

```
pd.DataFrame(model.history.history).plot()
```

11. To print Output

```
test_data=[]
test_image_o = cv2.imread('/content/drive/MyDrive/Colab Notebooks/FLOWERS/train/hibiscus/downlo
test_image = cv2.resize(test_image_o, (WIDTH, HEIGHT))
test_data.append(test_image)
test_data = np.array(test_image, dtype="float") / 255.0
test_data=test_data.reshape([-1,145, 182, 3])
pred = model.predict(test_data)
predictions = np.argmax(pred, axis=1)
print ("Prediction : "+categories[predictions[0]])
fig = plt.figure()
fig.patch.set_facecolor('xkcd:white')
plt.title(categories[predictions[0]])
plt.imshow(test_image_o)
```

VI. RESULT

Both the labels and the photos are expected. They deliver the outcome with a high degree of accuracy. RGB format will be used to represent the photos. The dataset is utilised to provide the images that are displayed. The same may be done with any image by building a user interface (UI) and deploying it with PyCharm or another programme. The user can then provide the appropriate input to get the image detection.

```
Prediction : hibiscus  
<matplotlib.image.AxesImage at 0x7fb3b4630ed0>
```


VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we describe a general model for flower detection based on a survey of various papers. This study uses a deep convolutional network to recognise flowers. The dataset folder named "flower" on the HDD was also used in the detection. The dataset can grow by including more flower categories. In this study, the system has potential for the future and is being used for architecture-based detection.

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